

Silver complex of 2-methyl-pyrimidine. Two dimensional coordination polymer

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Abstract : A novel metal-organic framework (MOF) of silver and 2-methylpyrimidine (2-Me-Pym) is described here. The compound crystallizes in the orthorhombic space group $P2_12_12$, with $a = 9.9842(8)$, $b = 11.6893(9)$ and $c = 9.2681(8)$ Å, and $R = 0.0301$. Ag^I is unsymmetrically coordinated with three pyrimidine-N centres of three 2-Me-Pym and forms coordination polymer. A metallomacrocycle, $Ag_6(2-Me-Pym)_6$, is constituted and repetition of this motif has generated two-dimensional polymer in a distorted honeycomb fashion.

Keywords : 2-Methylpyrimidine, silver complex, single crystal X-ray diffraction, hexametallal macrocycle.

Design and synthesis of metal organic framework (MOF) based on self-assembly of suitable building blocks to form coordination networks have attracted great attention in recent years because of its intriguing structures and potential applications in catalysis, separation, gas storage and molecular recognition¹⁻³. Formation of varieties of networks of metal complexes depends on the preferred coordination geometry of the metal, structure of the organic ligand, the metal to ligand ratio and the reaction condition. The MOF comprising of heterocyclic ligands like, imidazole, thiazole, pyridine and pyrimidine becoming are especially important to construct 1D, 2D and 3D coordination polymers⁴. Silver forms different types of complexes with these ligands⁵. There are several examples of pyrimidine complexes developed especially by Rogers's⁶ group. To the best of our knowledge there are no example of coordination complex of 2-methylpyrimidine, despite its simplicity and its coordination possibilities. This has encouraged us to develop the chemistry of 2-methylpyrimidine. Argentophilicity of *N*-heterocycle is well-known which leads to the generation of polymer network^{4,5}. The Ag-complex of this ligand has generated polymeric structure which displays an interesting topology. In this work we will report structural-characterization of Ag^I -2-Me-Pym by single crystal X-ray diffraction study.

Results and discussion

2-Methyl-pyrimidine (2-Me-Pym) is a simple ligand. Biomedical application of pyrimidine derivatives has attracted in the field of pharmaceutical and toxicological studies^{7,8}. The coordination chemistry of this molecule is yet to be explored.

In this work we are reporting first time Ag^I complex of this ligand. Upon reaction with $AgClO_4$ in methanol it has precipitated polymeric product. The composition of the complex is assigned as $[Ag_2(2-Me-Pym)_3](ClO_4)_2$ from microanalytical data. The compound is sparingly soluble in common organic solvents and hence the conductance and spectral data ($\Lambda_M = 48 \Omega^{-1} cm^{-2} mol^{-1}$) are collected in DMSO solution.

Table 1. Summarised crystallography data for $[Ag_2(2-Me-Pym)_3](ClO_4)_2$

Crystal parameters	
Empirical formula	$C_{15}H_{18}N_6Ag_2Cl_2O_8$
Formula weight	696.8
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Size, mm	$0.30 \times 0.10 \times 0.10$
Space group	$P2_12_12$
<i>T</i> (K)	296 (2)
<i>a</i> (Å)	9.9842 (8)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.6893 (9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	9.2681 (8)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1081.66 (13)
λ (Å)	0.71073
ρ_{calcd} (mg m ⁻³)	2.140
<i>Z</i>	2
μ ($M_o - K_{\alpha}$)/mm ⁻¹	2.115
Reflection collected	7340
Unique data [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	2609
Parameters	151
R_1^a	0.0301
wR_2^b	0.0885
GOF	1.05

$$^aR_1 = \sum |F_o - F_c| / \sum F_o, \quad ^b wR_2 = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2) / \sum wF_o^4]^{1/2}, \quad w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0600P)^2].$$

Fig. 1. Polymeric structure showing 30% probability displacement ellipsoids (ClO_4 and hydrogen removed for clarity).

The electronic absorption spectrum of the complex in DMSO solution shows intraligand charge transfer consisting of two intense sharp bands at 246 and 363 nm, attributed to $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ and $\pi^* \leftarrow n$ transitions. The complex is poorly fluorescent. Excitation of the molecule at 363 nm shows the fluorescence maxima at 450 nm. Infrared spectral measurement shows that ClO_4 appears at 1084 and 624 cm^{-1} along with other molecular stretchings at 1580–800 cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR data in DMSO- d_6 show that 2-Me proton appears at 3.33 ppm as singlet; 5-H appears as triplet at 6.64 ppm (J 7.0 Hz); 4- and 6-H appear as doublet at 8.30 ppm (J 6.75 Hz). The free ligand protons appear as follows : 2-Me, 3.22 ppm; 5-H, 6.51; 4- and 6-H, 8.13 (J 7.00 Hz). This signifies that the polymeric structure is retained in DMSO solution.

The structure of the compound has been established by single crystal X-ray diffraction data (Fig. 1). The structure consists of one crystallographically independent silver atom in a general position and there are three ligands per two silver atoms, it implies that at least one of the ligands must lie in some crystallographic symmetry element. The crystal structure shows that Me-2-Pym bridges two Ag atoms through two N-donor centres and propagates to generate 2D arrangement (Fig. 1). In the case of 2-amino-pyrimidine silver(I) forms polynuclear complex⁹ of variable dimension. 2-Hydroxypyrimidine (Hpymo) has also demonstrated the isolation of polymeric Ag^I complex, $[\text{Ag}(\text{pymo})]_n$ through the polymerization of cyclic $[\text{Ag}(\text{pymo})]_6$ species¹⁰. In each case pyrimidine is bridging two Ag^I centres by two pyrimidine-N centres. In the present case Ag^I is tri-coordinated with three Me-2-Pym and the Ag–N bond distances are substantially different (2.228–2.367 Å, selected parameters of geometry is listed in Table 2) which is in good agreement with corresponding distances of related complex^{11,12}. In the tri-coordinated environment of Ag, the smallest $\text{N}_{\text{pym}}-\text{Ag}-\text{N}_{\text{pym}}$ angle is 95.89° and the highest is 142.83°. It is noted that coordination of pyrimidine has generated a metallomacrocyclic of ‘ $\text{Ag}_6(2\text{-Me-Pym})_6$ ’ whose judicious repetition has built up some sort of distorted honeycomb fashion. The conformation of coordinated ligand in the macrocycle has reduced the formal cavity by blocking either sides with anion. This conformational arrangement has been reflected from torsional angles (Table 2).

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°)

	Distance (Å)		Angles (°)
Ag-N(1)	2.228(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(2)	142.82(11)
Ag-N(2)	2.305(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(3)	121.16(11)
Ag-N(3)	2.368(3)	N(2)-Ag-N(3)	95.89(11)
N(1)-C(3)	1.341(5)	Ag-N(2)-C(1)	119.2(3)
N(1)-C(4)	1.344(4)	Ag-N(2)-C(4)	119.8(2)
N(2)-C(1)	1.323(5)	Ag-N(3)-C(8)	124.7(3)
Cl-O(1)	1.415(3)	Ag-N(3)-C(6)	113.9(3)
Cl-O(2)	1.431(3)	O(4)-Cl-O(3)	112.0(4)
Cl-O(3)	1.414(4)	O(4)-Cl-O(1)	108.2(3)
Cl-O(4)	1.383(4)	O(3)-Cl-O(1)	106.1(3)
		O(4)-Cl-O(2)	111.2(3)
		O(1)-Cl-O(2)	107.5(2)
Torsion angles			
N(2)-Ag-N(3)-C(8)	24.0(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(3)-C(6)	49.2(3)
N(2)-Ag-N(3)-C(6)	-127.6(3)	N(1)-Ag-N(3)-C(8)	-159.2(2)
N(2)-Ag-N(1)-C(4)	-42.5(4)	N(3)-Ag-N(1)-C(4)	142.8(3)
N(2)-Ag-N(1)-C(3)	125.9(3)	N(3)-Ag-N(1)-C(3)	-48.7(3)

The charge of silver(I) in the polymeric unit is balanced by ClO_4^- penetrated in the layers of coordination polymer. Anion (ClO_4^-) is flanked in the layers through hydrogen bonding with the pyrimidine-H, the C–H–O bonds (Fig. 2),

Fig. 2. ClO_4^- is hydrogen bonded with pyrimidine-H and methyl-H and lines in the interlayer positions.

in which the length varies from 2.2 to 2.5 Å, [C(5)–H(5)–O(1) : C(5)–H(5), 0.96; H(5)–O(1), 2.23; C(5)–O(1), 3.079(4) Å and $\angle\text{C(5)–H(5)–O(1)}$, 146° (symmetry : $-x, -1-y, z$). C(5)–H(5)–O(2) : C(5)–H(5), 0.96; H(5)–O(2), 2.52; C(5)–O(2), 3.095(6) Å and $\angle\text{C(5)–H(5)–O(2)}$, 119° (symmetry, $x, -1+y, z$). C(5)–H(5)–N(3) : C(5)–H(5), 0.96; H(5)–N(3), 2.34; C(5)–N(3), 3.242(4) Å and $\angle\text{C(5)–H(5)–N(3)}$, 156° (symmetry : $1/2-x, -1/2+y, 1-z$). C(7)–H(7)–O(3) : C(7)–H(7), 0.93; H(7)–O(3), 2.48; C(7)–O(3), 3.102(9) Å and $\angle\text{C(7)–H(7)–O(3)}$, 132° (symmetry : $-x, 1-y, 1+z$). The molecule possess π - π and C–H- π interaction. The acceptable C–H- π interactions are C(9)–H(9)–Cg(1)[H(9)–Cg(1), 2.433(3) and C(9)–Cg(1), 3.380 Å, and $\angle\text{C(9)–H(9)–Cg(1)}$, $168.6(1)^\circ$ (symmetry : $1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1-z$). C(5)–H(5)–Cg(2). [H(5)–Cg(2), 2.530(1) and C(5)–Cg(2), 3.457 Å, and $\angle\text{C(5)–H(5)–Cg(2)}$, $162.3(3)^\circ$ (symmetry : $1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1-z$); where Cg(1)

= [N(1)–C(3)–C(2)–C(1)–N(2)–C(4)] and Cg(2) = [N(3)–C(6)–C(7)–C(6a)–N(3a)–C(8)]. Packing of Ag-(2-Me-Pym) polymer shows layers interacted through supramolecular interactions (Fig. 3). The acceptable π - π distance is 3.750 Å between Cg(1)–Cg(1') (Cg(1') symbolises adjacent pyrimidine centroid) (Fig. 4). In the structure there is no Ag–Ag interaction, the distance between two Ag atoms of two consecutive layers is 5.114 Å which is not interesting.

Conclusion :

This paper describes the silver complex of 2-methylpyrimidine. The complexes are characterized by different physicochemical methods and single crystal X-ray structure determination shows two-dimensional coordination polymer adjoining hexametallate macrocycle, $[\text{Ag}_6(2\text{-Me-Pym})_6]$.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

2-Methylpyrimidine (2-Me-Pym) has been synthesized by the reported procedure¹³. AgClO_4 was purchased from Fluka. Analytical grade solvents were received from Sisco Research Lab, Mumbai, India and used without further purification. Microanalyses (C, H and N) were performed using Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured from μ -304 Systronics conductivity meter in DMSO solution. Spectroscopic measurements were carried out using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra, Lambda 25 Perkin-Elmer; IR spectra (KBr disk, 4000–450 cm^{-1}), RX-1 Perkin-Elmer; ^1H NMR spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$, Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometers in presence of TMS as internal standard.

Fig. 3. Layers of coordination polymers are in packing interaction.

Fig. 4. π - π interaction packing view normal to (0,0,1).

Synthesis of $[Ag_2(2-Me-Pym)_3](ClO_4)_2$:

The title complex has been prepared by the reaction of Me-2-Pym with $AgClO_4$ in methanol at 1 : 1 metal to ligand ratio. 150 mg (1.60 mmol) Me-2-Pym and 221 mg (1.07 mmol) $AgClO_4$ were taken in MeOH and the solution was stirred for 4 h, the orange-yellow precipitate was collected by filtration and dried over $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator. Yield was 260 mg (70%). Microanalytical data; (Calculated), C, 25.83; H, 2.58; N, 12.06; Found : C, 25.77; H, 2.62; N, 12.14.

Crystallographic data collection and structure solution :

The block shaped crystals were developed from slow diffusion of diethyl ether into DMSO solution of the complex. Crystal dimension is $0.30 \times 0.10 \times 0.10$ mm. Data were collected (Table 1) by fine focus sealed tube at 296(2) K using monochromator Bruker Smart CCD Area Detector (Mo- $K\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). Unit cell parameters were determined from least-squares refinement of setting angles with 2θ in the range $4.40 \leq 2\theta \leq 56.64^\circ$. The hkl ranges were $-13 \leq h \leq 12$, $-15 \leq k \leq 13$, $-12 \leq l \leq 12$. Data were recorded using the ω scan technique and corrected for Lorentz polarization effects and for linear decay. Semi-empirical absorption corrections based on ψ -scans were applied. The structure was solved by direct method using SHELXS-97¹⁴ and successive difference Fourier syntheses. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using the riding model. In the final difference Fourier map the residual minima and maxima $(-0.735, 0.308 e/\text{Å}^3)$ were evaluated out using SHELXL-97¹⁵. All calculations were carried out using SHELXS-97¹⁴, SHELXL-97¹⁵, ORTEP-3¹⁶ and PLATON-99¹⁷ program.

Supplementary material :

Crystallographic data for the structure have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic data center, CCDC No. 637473 for $[Ag_2(2\text{-methyl-pyrimidine})_3](ClO_4)_2$. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www:http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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